

Proteomics and peptidomics to investigate the metabolic fate of food proteins

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Tracking the fate of dietary proteins in human body has special relevance to assess the impact of food on human health because food-derived (poly)peptides are virtually capable of inducing positive (health-promoting) or negative (allergy, adverse reactions) effects. However, it is a challenging task since a food protein “digestome” is a very complex biomolecular system that may combine thousands of variously sized peptides, free amino acids, undigested proteins, degradation products of macro- and micronutrients other than proteins as well as relatively abundant enzymes and compounds of the digestive tract.

Mass spectrometry (MS)-based proteomics and peptidomics have enabled us to tackle such a complexity. However, the information currently available about the fate of food proteins in humans is fragmentary since it results from *in vitro* or *ex vivo* digestion/absorption model systems, and no standardized analytical workflows exist yet. Recently, food-derived peptides have been detected in human body fluids (*i.e.*, breast milk, blood, urine) by high-resolution MS [1-4] providing clear evidence that specific food polypeptides survive digestive degradation, are absorbed, and distributed through the body, so that they might be responsible for effects on target organs. The most evident aspect emerging from our preliminary findings is that the fate of food proteins is affected by a wide interindividual variability [3], thus questioning in part the reliability of the model systems.

Understanding the kinetics of food protein digestion also paves the way to applications of “digestomics” in unexpected fields such as forensic sciences [5, 6].

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